

THE USE OF HIGH VISCOSITY ELASTOMERS TO ASSESS THE DEGREE OF FIXATION OF A COMPLETE MANDIBULAR REMOVABLE DENTURE

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Abstract

The results of assessing the quality of fixation of a complete removable prosthesis of the lower jaw by developed and traditional methods in patients with varying degrees of adaptation to such prostheses were analyzed.

Keywords: dental prosthetics, patients of different ages, loss of teeth

Prosthetics of patients with a complete absence of teeth in the lower jaw remains a difficult task in modern dentistry [1]. The replacement of the missing dentition is carried out, as a rule, by making a complete removable lamellar denture. One of the criteria for successful rehabilitation of patients with edentulous lower jaw is the fixation of a complete removable denture [4]. Following the principle of completeness of treatment, the doctor during the period of dispensary observation must evaluate the fixation of the complete prosthesis in order to, if necessary, correct it and give the patient the necessary recommendations. Usually, the fixation of such a prosthesis is assessed in the following ways: manually, when the doctor lifts the prosthesis with his fingers and evaluates the force required for this, and visually, the retention of the prosthesis on the alveolar process of the jaw during functional tests is assessed [1, 2]. However, these methods have disadvantages. These include the lack of a unified scheme for the implementation of these evaluation methods, which can lead to different results when repeated. The quality of fixation by these methods is assessed only with the patient's mouth open, which to a certain extent reduces the amount of information useful to the researcher, because the process of chewing and swallowing occurs with the mouth closed [3]. Therefore, the soft tissues surrounding the removable prosthesis are located differently and the true degree of fixation of the prosthesis may differ from the results obtained.

To obtain complete and comprehensive information about the quality of fixation of a complete removable denture, we offer an additional method for its evaluation. It is carried out as follows: a material available for use in the clinic is needed, the consistency of which is close to the consistency of a food bolus (we use the base layer of A-silicone), approximately 0.5 cm³ of such material is divided into two equal parts and placed on the occlusal surfaces of the fifth and sixth teeth of the patient's lower prosthesis on the right and

left, we ask you to close your teeth, after 3 seconds the patient opens his teeth and opens his mouth. We evaluate the results of the test: the prosthesis remained on the alveolar process of the lower jaw - the test is "positive", the prosthesis is held by the material at the upper teeth - the test is "negative". A feature of this method is physiological, i.e. implementation under conditions similar to the act of chewing, when the muscles adjacent to the prosthesis and other soft tissues do not have an effect on it that does not correspond to the physiological one. Also, the proposed method is easy to implement, has a clear protocol, does not require significant time and materials, and makes it easy to compare the results. Many researchers note a direct relationship between the fixation of the lower complete removable denture and the patient's adaptation to such a prosthesis, which is a necessary condition for successful orthopedic treatment [1, 2]. Adaptation to the prosthesis occurs gradually and is expressed in the development of neuromuscular coordination, restoration of impaired functions of speech, chewing and swallowing, which is impossible without sufficient fixation of the prosthesis [1]. The purpose of this study is to develop and determine the effectiveness of a new method for assessing the quality of fixation of a complete removable denture of the lower jaw.

Material and Research Methods.

The objects of this study were 172 patients with a complete absence of teeth in the lower jaw. Each of them was made a complete removable plate prosthesis. The study was conducted within a period of two weeks to two years after prosthetics, subject to the compliance of the prosthesis with aesthetic and medical and technical standards. First, the degree of adaptation of the patient to a removable prosthesis was determined. The essence of the applied technique lies in the patient's subjective assessment, on a three-point scale of all functional changes in the dentoalveolar apparatus, on a five-point scale - of general well-being and emotional mood after prosthetics.

Then, the fixation of the prosthesis was manually assessed - the researcher lifted the prosthesis by the front teeth with his fingers and assessed the force required for this, and the displacement of the prosthesis was visually determined during functional tests. Based on the results, a total assessment of prosthesis fixation was made. Then the evaluation was carried out by our proposed method using a high viscosity elastomer.

Research results and discussion

The smallest group (13 people) consisted of patients with a good degree of fixation of a complete removable denture: in order to separate the denture from the tissues of the prosthetic bed, a certain effort had to be applied. Patients in this group demonstrated the highest degree of adaptation to their prostheses ($90 \pm 2.5\%$). A test with a viscous material in all such patients was positive. The next largest group (28 people) included patients in whom the prostheses did not hold well on the alveolar process of the lower jaw, were easily displaced by contraction of the masticatory and mimic muscles. The degree of adaptation of such patients to complete removable dentures in the lower jaw was low, $25 \pm 4.7\%$. A test with a viscous material is negative in all patients of this group. The largest group (131 people) consisted of patients in whom the prosthesis was held on the alveolar process during movements of the lower jaw and during functional tests, but was separated from the tissues of the prosthetic bed with the fingers of the researcher without any effort. Conducting a test with a viscous material divided the patients of this group into two subgroups: patients in whom the test was negative (74 people) and patients with a positive test (57 people).

In patients with a negative test, the degree of adaptation was $44 \pm 10.6\%$, and in patients with a positive test, adaptation to the prosthesis was higher and

amounted to $70 \pm 9.3\%$. Thus, the test we proposed to determine the fixation of a complete removable denture in the lower jaw showed results similar to those obtained when assessing the fixation of the same prosthesis by conventional clinical techniques, both in conditions of good adaptation and in the absence of it. Under conditions of incomplete patient adaptation to the prosthesis, the assessment method proposed by us demonstrated greater sensitivity to the amount of adaptation, which is an important circumstance for dynamic monitoring of the patient. During the follow-up period after orthopedic treatment of patients with edentulous lower jaw, the proposed test with a viscous material is effective and allows obtaining objective data on the fixation of a complete removable denture, and can also be one of the criteria in a comprehensive assessment of the patient's adaptation to such a prosthesis. The method of conducting the test is simple, accessible, does not require additional staff training, expensive equipment and significant time costs, which allows us to recommend it for use in outpatient appointments of various dental health facilities.

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